

Diversity of myxomycetes from forest habitats leading to Casaroro and Pulang Bato Falls in Negros Oriental, Philippines

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Abstract: We surveyed and report herein the assemblages and diversity of myxomycetes along forest habitats of Casaroro and Pulangbato Falls in Valencia, Negros Oriental, Philippines. Various plant-based substrates were collected randomly at three sampling points in each study area and used to prepare moist chamber cultures. From the 480 moist chambers prepared in this study, 381 were positive for myxomycetes and resulted in the identification of 34 species belonging to 15 genera. The forest areas leading to Casaroro Falls had higher taxonomic diversity than those of Pulangbato Falls. The study areas shared high similarity in species composition with 20 species in common. This study contributes to the species of myxomycetes reported in Negros Island, the third largest island in the Philippine archipelago.

Keywords: biodiversity indices, moist chamber culture technique, myxogastrids, slime molds, tropical forests

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Introduction

Myxomycetes are a unique yet diverse group of amoeboid, eukaryotic microorganisms which has been previously categorized under the Kingdoms Plantae, Fungi, and Animalia (Martin and Alexopoulos 1969; Olive 1975; Spiegel et al. 2004), but is currently classified under the Kingdom Protista, Super Class Amoebozoa, and Class Eumycetozoa (Adl et al. 2005; Keller and Everhart 2010). As microbial predators, myxomycetes, also known as plasmodial slime molds, feed on microorganisms such as bacteria, yeasts, and fungal spores, and may play important roles in nutrient cycling and forest productivity (Keller and Braun 1999). Their complex life cycle is composed of a haploid, uninucleate amoeboid or a flagellated swarm cell, and a diploid, multinucleate plasmodial stage, which form intricate fruiting bodies with haploid spores when exposed to harsh or drying conditions unfavourable for their survival (Everhart and Keller 2008; Dagamac et al. 2015b).

Myxomycetes have been recorded in every known terrestrial habitat with some species from aquatic habitats (Lindley et al. 2007), although most of what is known about myxomycetes is derived from studies conducted in temperate forests. While species have been reported from edges of melting

snowbanks and other temperate forest habitats (Novozhilov *et al.* 2013, 2020; Liu *et al.* 2015; Stephenson 2021), myxomycetes have also been recorded in montane and coastal forests in both the Paleotropics (dela Cruz *et al.* 2014; Dagamac *et al.* 2015b; Macabago *et al.* 2012, 2017; Eloreta *et al.* 2020; Pecundo *et al.* 2020; Cabutaje *et al.* 2021) and the Neotropics (Ogata *et al.* 1996; Lado and Rojas 2018; Treviño-Zevallos and Lado 2020; Rincón-Marín *et al.* 2021). According to dela Cruz *et al.* (2014), there is possibly more records of myxomycetes in the tropics than reported and perhaps in similar number to those from the temperate regions. Although there is a higher chance of endemism and diversity in the tropics, knowledge about the myxomycetes existing in tropical areas is still insufficient, an example of which are the island forests in tropical Philippines.

Today, a total of 167 myxomycete species have been recorded in the Philippines based on previous surveys (Dagamac & dela Cruz, 2015, 2019; Macabago *et al.* 2020a; Cabutaje *et al.* 2021), but these surveys have not yet covered many island forest ecosystems. For example, in the Visayas region in the central part of the Philippine archipelago, few isolated islands were studied so far. Macabago *et al.* (2017) had earlier reported 54 species and 20 genera in Bohol Island, the tenth largest island in the country with an area of approximately 3 860 km². Myxomycetes were identified from plant-based substrates collected from a grassland, a woodland, a coastal forest, and natural islet or reef forests, and even in an agricultural plantation. The study of Alfaro *et al.* (2014) also reported 28 species and 14 genera from a lowland montane forest and an agricultural plantation in Negros Occidental, part of the Negros Island, but none so far in its sister province, Negros Oriental, which is in the Southeastern side of the island.

The province of Negros Oriental is also known for its nature attractions bringing local and foreign tourists to the area. Among these nature attractions are the Casaroro and Pulangbato Falls located in the municipality of Valencia. Casaroro Falls is considered as the most photographed waterfall in the province while Pulangbato Falls is equally visited for its nearby resorts. The genuine charms of these waterfalls make them the two most visited tourism hot spots in the province. Along the trails leading to these waterfalls are forest habitats that can be easily surveyed for myxomycetes. The different man-made disturbances brought about by eco-tourism and other anthropogenic activities may possibly impact the diversity of myxomycetes in these areas. During our field expedition in July 2017, we observed evidence of man-made disturbances such as slash-and-burn activity to clear certain areas of the forest for conversion to agricultural use and the construction of resort infrastructures. This serves as our primary motivation to conduct this study. Hence, this paper documents for the first time the assemblages of myxomycetes present in these forest habitats leading to Casaroro and Pulangbato Falls. Also, a comparison of species diversity was performed, thereby contributing to the existing information on myxomycetes in Negros Island, the Philippines and the Asian Paleotropics. This information is expected to provide baseline data for future comparisons intended to gain insights on the possible effects of man-made disturbances on myxomycete diversity.

Materials and methods

Study Areas

Forested areas along the waterfall stream path leading to and near Casaroro Falls (CF) and Pulangbato Falls (PF) in the municipality of Valencia, Negros Oriental served as the collecting localities in this study (Fig. 1). The municipality of Valencia has a total land area of 14 749 hectares, 65% of which is considered mountainous with an elevation ranging from 200 to 500 meters above sea level. The sampling areas leading to the two waterfalls are characterized with a very steep slope and a moderate canopy closure. Both sites have a type III climate with no very pronounced season, i.e., wet from June to November and relatively dry for the rest of the year. Average annual temperature and rainfall were

recorded to be at 27.8°C and 900 mm, respectively. In each collecting locality, three sampling points were chosen randomly along the trails leading to the waterfalls for the collection of substrates. Evidence of anthropogenic disturbances like slash-and-burn activity for forest clearing and construction of resort infrastructures were observed. The GPS coordinates of the six sampling points were as follows: CF1 (9°16'40''N, 123°12'10''E), CF2 (9°16'48''N, 123°12'23''E), CF3 (9°16'49''N, 123°12'26''E), PF1 (9°19'16''N, 123°11'32''E), PF2 (9°19'20''N, 123°11'39''E), and PF3 (9°19'12''N, 123°11'24''E).

Figure 1. Map and images of the two collecting localities: Casaroro Falls and Pulangbato Falls in Negros Oriental, Philippines. Indicated as dots are the three sampling points per collecting locality.

Collection of Field Specimens and Substrates

Collection of field specimens and substrata was carried out in the two localities during our expedition in July 2017. The forested areas along the trails leading to the two waterfalls were surveyed for any visible fruiting bodies of myxomycetes. As a complementary technique to increase the number of species, 30 samples each of ground leaf litter (GL) and twigs (TW) and 20 samples of other substrates (collectively referred to as OS, e.g., woody vines, dried fruits, inflorescences, ferns or macrofungi) were collected via opportunistic sampling strategy in each of the three sampling points per locality (=240 collected substrates per collecting area). These samples were used to prepare 480 moist chambers. The collected substrates were placed in properly labelled brown paper bags, and then transported and air-dried in the laboratory prior to the preparation of moist chamber cultures.

Preparation of Moist Chambers

Air-dried samples of ground leaf litter, twigs, and other substrates were cut into postage stamp-sized pieces (for leaf-based materials) or about 2 inches in length (for twigs or woody substrates) and placed on disposable Petri dishes lined with paper towels following the protocol described by Stephenson and Stempen (1994). The moist chamber set-ups were flooded with distilled water for 24 hours. After which, the pH of the substrates was measured using a pH meter (Milwaukee pH600) and the excess water

was poured off. The moist chambers were maintained under diffuse light at room temperature and were checked regularly for the presence of myxomycetes, either as plasmodia or fruiting bodies, for eight weeks. Mature fruiting bodies obtained from the moist chambers were removed and pasted inside small cardboard boxes.

Characterization and Identification of Myxomycetes

The morphological features of the fruiting bodies were determined with the use of a dissecting microscope (BestScope BS-3040 Zoom Binocular Stereo Microscope). The fruiting body characteristics observed in the study were the fruiting body type, size, shape, color, external structures, stalk, and the presence and absence of lime. In addition, internal structures (e.g., spores, columella, and capillitium) were also examined using a compound light microscope (Olympus Light Microscope CX31-12C04). For this part, spore mass from the fruiting bodies was mounted on a clean glass slide with the use of potassium hydroxide as the mounting medium. The spore morphologies such as the ornamentation, size, shape, and color were also documented. Identification of the species was done by comparing specimens with descriptions in the published literature and web-based identification keys available for myxomycetes such as the Eumycetozoa Project (<http://slimemold.uark.edu/>). The names of all identified myxomycetes were confirmed using an online nomenclatural database for the eumycetozoa (<http://nomen.eumycetozoa.com>, Lado 2005–2021).

Ecological Analysis

Moist Chamber Productivity. To analyze the moist chamber productivity of each substrate and collecting locality, values of percent yield was computed. The presence of fruiting bodies and/or plasmodia in a single moist chamber was considered as one positive collection. The number of moist chambers positive for myxomycetes was divided by the total number of moist chambers prepared, then multiplied by 100.

Relative Abundance. To analyze the occurrence of species on a substrate and collecting locality, the relative abundance was computed based on its presence or absence in a positive moist chamber. Abundance index (AI) was computed as the total number of recorded myxomycetes divided by the total number of myxomycete collections. Each species was then ranked based on the abundance indices of Stephenson et al. (1993): abundant (A) if it represented $\geq 3.0\%$ of the total myxomycetes in the collection, common (C) if the RA value was $\geq 1.5\%$ but $< 3.0\%$, occasional (O) if the RA value was $\geq 0.5\%$ but $< 1.5\%$, and rare (R) if the RA value was $< 0.5\%$.

Taxonomic and Species Diversity. Taxonomic diversity index (TDI), also known as S/G ratio, was calculated as the ratio of the recorded species and genera. The TDI value is inversely proportional to its taxonomic diversity, and thus, a low S/G ratio indicates a higher overall taxonomic diversity (Dagamac et al. 2014). Different diversity indices were also used to compute species diversity as described by Stephenson (1989) and Dagamac et al. (2012): Shannon diversity index (H_S), Gleason Index (H_G) and Pielou's species evenness index (E). Moreover, to generate the Fisher's Alpha Index and Simpson's Index, the web-based software, Species Prediction and Diversity Estimation (SPADE) was used (Chao and Shen, 2010). Data from the moist chamber cultures were used to generate a species list and the number of records. These were eventually used to compute species diversity.

Community Comparison. To assess the similarities between the study sites and substrate types (GL vs TW), the Sørensen's Coefficient of Community (CC) and the Percentage Similarity (PS) were calculated as described by Stephenson (1989). The CC value ranges from 0 (when no species are present in both communities) to 1 (when all species are present in both communities). The PS considers both the presence or absence of species and their relative abundance (Stephenson 1988, 1989). These community analyses have been used in biodiversity and ecological studies involving myxomycetes (Stephenson et al.

2000, Dagamac *et al.* 2012). Lastly, to present the distribution and the shared species between the two collecting localities and substrata, Venn diagrams were constructed.

Results

In this study, a total of 480 moist chamber cultures were prepared, of which 381 (or 79%) were positive for myxomycetes either as plasmodia or fruiting bodies. The moist chamber productivity was also computed as 70% and 89% for samples collected in Casaroro Falls and Pulangbato Falls, respectively. A total of 34 species belonging to 15 genera were recorded in this study from both the field and moist chamber collections (Table 1). Casaroro Falls had 25 recorded species (Fig. 2) as compared to the 29 species tallied for Pulangbato Falls (Fig. 3). Most of the recorded species were obtained from moist chamber cultures. Only 10 species representing six genera from 13 collections were obtained directly from the field and were identified as *Arcyria cinerea*, *A. incarnata*, *Collaria arcyrionema*, *Cribraria macrocarpa*, *Didymium nigripes*, *D. squamulosum*, *Hemitrichia calyculata*, *Stemonitopsis typhina*, *Stemonitis fusca*, and *Stemonitis axifera*, the last as the most common with three collections.

Figure 2. Representative myxomycetes collected from Casaroro Falls, Negros Oriental. (A) *Arcyria cinerea*, (B) *Comatricha tenerrima*, (C) *Didymium effusum*, (D) *Perichaena depressa*, (E) *Physarum cinereum*, (F) *Physarum decipiens*.

Our results indicated that *Arcyria cinerea* (61 collections) was the most recorded species followed by *Didymium squamulosum* (53 collections), *Perichaena chrysosperma* (32 collections), *Perichaena depressa* (27 collections), *Diderma hemisphaericum* (27 collections), *Comatricha tenerrima* (21

collections), *Perichaena pedata* (17 collections), *Diderma effusum* (16 collections), and *Didymium nigripes* 13 collections). All were described as abundant. Other species were recorded as common (11), occasional (7), and rare (7). The annotated species list of myxomycetes recorded in the forest areas leading to the two waterfalls is shown in Table 1. The number of records per species per collection site and per substrate type was provided with an estimation of abundance given in the last column.

Table 1. Frequency and Abundance Index (AI) of myxomycetes in the two collecting localities.

Taxa	Collecting localities								Frequency	AI ^b
	Casaroro Falls				Pulangbato Falls					
	GL ^a	TW	OS	FC	GL	TW	OS	FC		
<i>Arcyria cinerea</i>	10	9	4	-	13	13	11	1	61	A
<i>Arcyria denudata</i>	-	2	2	-	-	3	-	-	7	C
<i>Arcyria incarnata</i>	-	-	-	1	-	1	-	-	2	O
<i>Ceratiomyxa fruticulosa</i>	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	3	C
<i>Clastoderma debaryanum</i>	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	2	C
<i>Collaria arcyriionema</i>	-	-	-	-	2	1	-	1	4	C
<i>Comatracha nigra</i>	-	1	-	-	-	3	-	-	4	C
<i>Comatracha pulchella</i>	-	2	1	-	1	2	-	-	6	C
<i>Comatracha tenerrima</i>	-	5	3	-	1	12	-	-	21	A
<i>Cribraria microcarpa</i>	-	-	-	1	-	1	1	-	3	C
<i>Cribraria violacea</i>	1	2	1	-	1	1	-	-	6	C
<i>Diachea leucopodia</i>	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	1	R
<i>Diachea splendens</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	R
<i>Diderma effusum</i>	2	-	1	-	12	1	-	-	16	A
<i>Diderma hemisphaericum</i>	12	-	-	-	12	1	2	-	27	A
<i>Didymium bahiense</i>	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	1	R
<i>Didymium nigripes</i>	2	-	1	1	5	3	1	-	13	A
<i>Didymium squamulosum</i>	8	1	3	1	37	-	3	-	53	A
<i>Hemitrichia calyculata</i>	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1	R
<i>Hemitrichia serpula</i>	-	-	-	-	1	4	-	-	5	O
<i>Lamproderma scintillans</i>	3	1	-	-	3	2	-	-	9	C
<i>Perichaena chryosperma</i>	-	6	8	-	6	10	2	-	32	A
<i>Perichaena corticalis</i>	-	1	1	-	-	3	-	-	5	O
<i>Perichaena depressa</i>	-	12	-	-	12	3	-	-	27	A
<i>Perichaena pedata</i>	-	-	13	-	1	3	-	-	17	A
<i>Physarum cinereum</i>	1	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	2	O
<i>Physarum compressum</i>	-	-	-	-	2	4	-	-	6	C
<i>Physarum decipiens</i>	-	1	1	-	-	4	-	-	6	O
<i>Physarum oblatum</i>	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	1	R
<i>Physarum superbum</i>	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	1	R
<i>Stemonitis axifera</i>	-	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	3	O
<i>Stemonitis fusca</i>	1	2	-	-	2	1	-	1	7	C
<i>Stemonitis splendens</i>	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	1	R
<i>Stemonitopsis typhina</i>	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	2	O
Total	41	46	40	10	116	80	20	3	356	

^aSubstrates: GL – ground leaf litter, TW – twigs, OS – other substrates, FC – field collection

^bAbundance Index: R = rare (<0.5%), O = occasional (>0.5–1.5%), C = common (>1.5–3 %), A = abundant (>3% of the total collections)

Taxonomic and species diversity values are presented in Table 2. Casaroro Falls had a higher taxonomic diversity (TDI=1.92) than Pulangbato Falls (TDI=2.42). Such can also be said of its species diversity with Casaroro Falls recording higher values than Pulangbato Falls, albeit the H_G was greater for Pulangbato Falls owing to the higher number of species recorded in this area and the FAI and SID were relatively similar between the two collecting localities.

Table 2. Taxonomic and species diversity values of myxomycetes in the two collecting localities.

Sites	Number of species	Number of genera	TDI	H_s	H_G	E	FAI	SID
Casaroro Falls	25	13	1.92	1.21	4.88	0.57	8.95	0.08
Pulangbato Falls	29	12	2.42	0.91	5.20	0.39	8.98	0.09

^aDiversity Indices: TDI – taxonomic diversity index or S/G ratio, H_s – Shannon diversity index, H_G – Gleason index of species richness, E – Pielou’s index of species evenness, FAI – Fisher’s alpha index, SID – Simpson’s index of diversity

Figure 3. Representative species of myxomycetes collected from Pulangbato Falls, Negros Oriental. (A) *Arcyria denudata*, (B) *Ceratiomyxa fruticulosa*, (C) *Collaria arcyrionema*, (D) *Diderma hemisphaericum*, (E) *Perichaena chrysosperma*, (F) *Stemonitis fusca*.

The similarities between the two collecting localities were computed as high (CC=0.74, PS=0.74), indicating that more than 70% of the recorded species in this study were present in both sites (Fig. 4). In

fact, Casaroro Falls and Pulangbato Falls have 20 species in common. However, between substrates, 5 species were shared by GL and TW in Casaroro Falls while a relatively higher number, 15 shared species, was noted for Pulangbato Falls. Comparing the other collected substrates (OS) with these two substrata, 3-4 species were common to all substrate types (Table 1). Nine species recorded from other substrates were found also in either GL or TW in Casaroro Falls while only two species were recorded in either GL or TW in Pulangbato Falls. One species, *Perichaena pedata* (13 collections) were recorded exclusively in other substrates.

Figure 4. Venn diagrams showing similarities in species composition of myxomycetes between Casaroro Falls and Pulangbato Falls and between the collected substrates (GL vs TW) in the two collecting localities. The coefficient of community (CC) and percentage similarity (PS) values are also provided.

Discussion

The Philippines offers many forest habitats for surveying myxomycetes. Among those so far studied are the forest patch in Anda Island (Kuhn et al. 2013), an urban ecopark (Macabago et al. 2010), forest reserves within watersheds (dela Cruz et al., 2010; Atayde et al., 2012), an inland forest in a lake (Isagan et al., 2020), and other tropical forests sites (Dagamac et al. 2015a; Cabutaje et al. 2021).

In Negros Island, Alfaro et al. (2014) conducted the first survey which reported 28 species. This island is also known for its many nature attractions that bring local and foreign tourists. Among these are the Casaroro Falls and Pulangbato Falls in Negros Oriental. It has been widely observed that luxuriant vegetation grows along the streams originating from waterfalls. It can also be deduced that the relatively high humidity, moist condition, and cooler temperature near these waterfalls provide favourable conditions for the growth of myxomycetes. Several studies have already suggested that myxomycete diversity is higher in habitats with increased humidity (Stephenson 1989; Ogata et al. 1996; Treviño-Zevallos and Lado 2020) and might have explained the high number of collections (=356) in this study. However, other studies contradicted this notion with Schnittler and Stephenson (2000) even stating that excess moisture in moist tropical forests does not favor the growth and support the further development of myxomycetes. Dagamac et al. (2014) also recorded more species of myxomycetes during samples collected in the dry season than in wet season.

Herein, we observed a high level of moist chamber productivity with 79% showing evidence of myxomycetes. This is comparable with the moist chamber productivity reported in other studies conducted in the Philippines such as the karst forests in Quezon (82%, Dagamac et al. 2015c) and Palawan (73%, Pecundo et al. 2017), the lowland mountain forests in the Bicol peninsula (74%, Dagamac et al. 2015a) and Mindoro Island (71%, Pecundo et al. 2020), and in the island forests of Caramoan and Coron (76%, Macabago et al. 2020a, 2020b). The present study identified 34 species belonging to 15 genera, 31 of which were derived from 480 moist chamber cultures (Table 1). This gave a proportion value of 0.06 species per MC and similar to the value recorded in the study of Alfaro et al. (2014) in Negros Occidental. Comparing the two sites, Casaroro Falls which recorded a lower number of species had a proportion value of 0.08 species per MC, also much lower than the proportion value of 0.12 species per MC in Pulangbato Falls.

As myxomycetes are influenced by microhabitats (Stephenson 1989), we may observe that a species is recorded rarely in one site but abundantly in another one. *Arcyria cinerea* and *Didymium squamulosum* are among the most abundant species reported in the Philippines by Carascal et al. (2017), Pecundo et al. (2017), Eloreta et al. (2020), and Cabutaje et al. 2021) as also in this study. However, we recorded only one collection of *Diachea leucopodia* while this species has been reported previously as either common or abundant (Rea-Maminta et al. 2015; Pecundo et al. 2020; Cabutaje et al. 2021). While our study initially aims to survey only ground leaf litter and twigs in the two collecting localities, the presence of other substrates in our sampling sites which could harbour other unique myxomycetes compelled us to collect these for moist chambers cultures. True enough, we recorded 13 myxomycetes from these other substrates (i.e., woody vines, dried fruits, inflorescences, ferns, and mushrooms), in Casaroro Falls, while six species were recovered from the same substrates in Pulangbato Falls. Many unique substrates have been shown as good microhabitats for myxomycetes, e.g., inflorescence (Schnittler and Stephenson 2002), grass litter (Carascal et al. 2017), barks (Policina and dela Cruz 2020a, 2020b), and even animal dung (Stephenson 1989).

To evaluate the diversity of myxomycetes along the forest habitats leading to Casaroro Falls and Pulangbato Falls, we used different diversity indices, all of which have been used in the study of myxomycetes (Table 2). We observed a higher taxonomic diversity expressed as TDI for Casaroro Falls over Pulangbato Falls, albeit the latter site was more species rich as expressed by HG. According to Stephenson et al. (1993), a biota in which the species are divided among many genera is more “intuitively”

diverse in a taxonomic sense than in a biota which the species belong to a few genera. We also obtained a higher species diversity expressed as H_s for Casaroro Falls while the FAI and SID values were almost similar. We noted a relatively high number of shared species (=20) between the two collecting localities, also reflected by a relatively high CC and PS values (Fig. 4). Perhaps, the similarities in environmental condition and the proximity of the two collecting localities may have accounted for this. Other studies that reported high shared species between sites of closer proximity were that of Macabago *et al.* (2016) with 29 species common between coastal and mountain forests of Lubang Island and of Cabutaje *et al.* (2021) with 20 shared species between beach and inland forests in Aurora and 23 shared species between the same forest types in Quezon.

It is interesting to note that although the species composition may be similar for the two communities being compared in this study, these species may differ in their abundance. For example, *Diderma effusum* was abundant in Pulangbato Falls (13 collections) but not in Casaroro Falls (3 collections). *Didymium squamulosum* follows the same pattern, with 40 collections in Pulangbato Falls and only 13 collections in Casaroro Falls. During our field expedition we observed a great deal of human-induced disturbance in Pulangbato Falls than in Casaroro Falls. Thus, it would be an interesting line of investigation if the observed abundance for some species of myxomycetes could be correlated with or due to these anthropogenic activities. If we look at the previous studies of Dagamac *et al.* (2015a, 2015b), the diversity of species was greatest in ecosystems with an intermediate degree of disturbance. However, these studies were not designed for the purpose of analysing disturbance as with the present study. In contrast, Rojas and Stephenson (2013) found no differences in a series of indicators among disturbance categories in their study design that actually looked at the effect of forest disturbance in the southwestern Peruvian Amazon on myxomycetes. Therefore, it would be an interesting topic for future research to look at how man-made disturbance might have affected the distribution and diversity of myxomycetes and if such impact could be true for all ecosystems inhabited by myxomycetes. A very careful experimental design is needed for this type of research to come up with a meaningful and relevant conclusion.

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